

SEVENTH FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME

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[Innovative tools for the future coordinated and stable operation of the pan-European electricity transmission system]

Project Deliverable

Deliverable D2.2 “Report on methods for system state forecasting”

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List of Symbols

Indices/sets

C	set of forecast conditions
EXC	cross-border exchange
$i \in 1, \dots, I$	grid node
$k \in 1, \dots, K$	look-ahead time
$sim \in 1, \dots, N$	simulation
S	set of system states
$t \in 1, \dots, T$	time
v	vertical (load)
$z \in 1, \dots, Z$	control zone

Parameters

n_c	number of contingencies
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Variables

dow	day of the week
E	forecast error
F	cumulative distribution function
hod	hour of the day
P	active power
ΔP_{sim}	simulated deviation from the active power forecast
Q	reactive power
ΔQ_{sim}	simulated deviation from the reactive power forecast
tod	type of day

List of abbreviations

AI	A rtificial i ntelligence
APF	A ctual p ower f low
ANN	A rtificial n eural n etwork
DACF	D ay- a head c ongestion f orecast
DAEF	D ay- a head e xchange f orecast
DOW	D escription o f w ork
ECAB	E uropean c ontrol a reas b alancing m odel
entso-e	E uropean N etwork of T ransmission S ystem O perators for E lectricity
RES	R enewable e nergy s ources
SN	S napshot
SUC	s ystem u se c ase
TSO	T ransmission s ystem o perator

1 Introduction

1.1 Outline and Framework of this Deliverable

This deliverable is a report of the work done in the framework of the Umbrella project in task 2.4 and 2.5 of Work Package 2 as defined in the description of work (DOW) of the Umbrella project [1]. The individual titles of the tasks according to the DOW [[1], p. 8] are:

1. Deriving forecast distributions for the system state,
2. Forecast of Critical System States.

In the DOW [[1], p. 9] the contents of the Deliverable 2.2 are outlined as follows:

Report on methods for system state forecasting: Report on methods for system state forecasting including uncertainties and critical system states.

The deliverable at hand is structured as follows. The second section of chapter 0 provides some background information on the UMBRELLA project and motivates this deliverable. Chapter 2 defines system states and system state parameters and compares the current operational planning framework with a probabilistic one developed within the UMBRELLA project. The modelling of relevant uncertainties for operational planning, which is elaborated in the Deliverable 2.1 [2], is briefly recalled in chapter 3 due to its importance for system state modelling. Chapter 4 describes how the simulated uncertainties are merged in order to run load flow calculation and compute system state parameter distributions. The influence of the disregarded uncertainties is also discussed in chapter 4. Finally, the identification and forecasting of critical system states is described in chapter 5. Chapter 6 concludes.

This deliverable was compiled under the lead of the University of Duisburg-Essen. Further participants were the Forschungsgemeinschaft für elektrische Anlagen und Stromwirtschaft e.V. (FGH).

1.2 Background

The energy landscape of Europe has been altered heavily in recent years. Besides the liberalization of the electricity market, the climate policy of the European Union (EU) that also defines targets for the electricity generation by renewable energy sources (RES) has important implications for the operation of the European transmission system. Uncertainties on the demand side, namely load forecasting uncertainties, are well-known and under control for years in terms of forecasting accuracy. On the supply side, the uncertainty of power plant outages was the major concern transmission system operators (TSOs) had to face for many years. Nowadays, we witness a strong shift in the power system due to growing energy generation from RES. This has not only consequences on the supply side, but also on the demand side, because many wind and solar farms feed into subordinate grids, which is not directly observable by the TSOs. Especially the intermittent nature of wind requires methods to anticipate changes of wind and, thus, wind power production. However,

no forecast is perfect. In order to cope with the forecast error, it is necessary to know the possible magnitude of under- or overestimations and its probabilities, so that TSOs are enabled to identify potential risks for a secure operation of their respective control area early and start the necessary actions to prevent such system states. This is one of the major objectives of Work Package 2.

Besides the forecast error, the increasing amount of RES also has an impact on intraday trades and, hence, on the secure operation of the grid. If the energy output of wind or solar power farms deviates from the expected output, conventional power plants have to adjust their power output accordingly. In as far as the decision of changing the power plant output is driven by purely commercial factors, the adjustment of the conventional power plants might jeopardize the system security even more. To predict the mentioned adjustments and the resulting changes of power flows as well as their uncertainty is also a major contribution of Work Package 2.

Most of the mentioned processes are more or less easy to predict individually. However, TSOs have limited information on the detail of these processes, but can only observe an aggregation of them (vertical grid load). This makes the collection of data and its use more difficult. Figure 1-1 illustrates this situation graphically.

Having analyzed all the main uncertainties and being able to forecast them would lead to an amount of data and information that is hard to handle for TSOs. Thus, the uncertainties and especially the correlation between uncertainties at different sites in the grid have to be translated into a standard that provides meaningful and quick decision guidance for TSOs. How to achieve a descriptive overall system state description is also part of the deliverable at hand. Furthermore, it is described how the critical system states among all possible system states are identified and how they can be forecasted.

Figure 1-1: Observable and non-observable influence factors

2 System states in operational planning

One of the main objectives of the operational planning process carried out by TSOs is the forecasting of future system states. The forecasts are obtained by predicting factors which influence the system state significantly. System states are described quantitatively by system state parameters, which are directly influenced by one or several factors. The concept is depicted in Figure 2-1.

Figure 2-1: Interdependency between system state, system parameters and factors

The system state can be described by the system state parameters A to n. System state parameter A is determined by the two factors 1 and 2, whereas system state parameter B is influenced by three factors etc.

Subsequently, section 0 carries out a definition of system state parameters. In order to build a common foundation and, once again, motivate this research work, section 2.2 explains quickly the current operational planning framework. Section 2.3 elaborates how the operational planning process within the UMBRELLA project, which is capable of integrating uncertainties, is designed.

2.1 Definition of system state parameters

The transmission system is in a certain quasi-stationary state at any point in time. A system state relevant for the operational planning process can be described by system state parameters. For operational planning purposes, the choice of system state parameters should be influenced by the relevance of the respective parameter, the parameter's information value and the time necessary to process given information. Given that, the system parameters:

- Node voltages and
- Branch currents

are chosen for the purpose of operational planning.

The transmission system is usually visualized as a graph model with nodes connected by edges/branches. A simple example of a system represented by a node-branch model with three nodes and branches is given in Figure 2-2.

Figure 2-2: Exemplary node-branch model

The state of the system in Figure 2-2 is described by the three node voltages U_A , U_B and U_C and the branch currents $I_{A \rightarrow B}$, $I_{A \rightarrow C}$ and $I_{C \rightarrow B}$. A forecast of future system states requires a prediction of all relevant factors determining the system state parameters (cf. Figure 2-1).

How these system state parameters and their factors are computed by the members of the “European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity” (entso-e) according to the current Continental Europe Operation Handbook [3] is explained subsequently. How they can be derived considering uncertainties in the operational planning process and how they can be forecasted is the main subject of the deliverable at hand.

2.2 Current operational planning framework

The current day-ahead congestion forecast (DACF) procedure executed by members of entso-e is shown in Figure 2-3 in a simplified way for the TSO A. One of the purposes of the DACF procedure is to identify potential congestions and contingencies by forecasting the quasi-stationary system state one day in advance. The basis for a determination of system state parameters is the deterministic prediction of uncertain factors influencing the system state parameters node voltages and branch currents. The most relevant factors are loads and in-feeds at each grid node. These two factors determine the use of the system represented by the box on the upper right hand side of Figure 2-3. The topology of the network, depicted at the upper left hand side of the figure also has a significant impact on the system state. Lastly, the power exchange with neighboring interconnected control areas is relevant for the determination of the system state as well. This factor is covered by the box in the upper middle of Figure 2-3 labeled with “Control Program of TSO A”. The forecast of power exchanges is basically derived from the registered and scheduled trades for the next day.

Figure 2-3: Scheme of DACF procedure of TSO A according to [3]

Based on the expected network topology, the power exchanges and the use of the system, system states for all 24 hours of the next day are determined separately by running load-flow calculations. Subsequently, TSO A adjusts the model of the system by e.g. applying topology measures.

In order to get a complete DACF for the entire entso-e region, the data sets of all participating TSOs have to be merged including a preceding adjustment of control programs using the VULCANUS system [3].

2.3 Operational planning framework accounting for uncertainties

Naturally, the current DACF procedure based on deterministic forecasts does not allow for any consideration of uncertainties. Presently, the system use case (SUC) is derived by aggregating all load and in-feeds at all nodes of the network. The result is the balance for every node, which is shown in Figure 2-4.

Figure 2-4: Aggregation of loads and in-feeds at an exemplary transmission node

However, certain factors such as wind power forecasts are subject to uncertainty. The main concept of this deliverable is to describe a methodology that facilitates the incorporation of probabilistic forecasts in the operational planning process based on the current DACF approach. The result is a set of forecasts representing deviations from the deterministic DACF and their probabilities. This can be interpreted as an extension of the DACF process with additional input factors. The resulting structure is defined as DACF+ dataset in the course of this document. In order to incorporate the uncertainties of different types of in-feeds and load into the DACF+, they have to be considered separately for the SUCs. This is depicted in Figure 2-5.

Figure 2-5: Separate consideration of different factors determining SUCs

While considering uncertainty factors and their occurrence, the interaction between uncertainty factors has to be regarded as well. As can be seen in Figure 2-6, the uncertainty of RES in-feeds and load can influence the control program. As an example, more wind in-feeds than expected in one control zone might lead to an increase of exports into neighbouring control zones. Additionally, unexpected changes on the load side and the control program will inescapably cause trades in the intraday markets, which changes the original production schedules. Which uncertainty factors are considered exactly and how they can be modelled is explained in chapter 3. How these uncertainties are used to compute system state parameters and their distributions is elaborated in chapter 4. Chapter 5 focuses on the forecast of critical system states.

Figure 2-6: Probabilistic operational planning framework

3 Modelling of relevant uncertainties for operational planning of transmission systems

Relevant uncertainties for operational planning of transmission grids can be classified into directly observable and unobservable uncertainty factors (see Figure 1-1). In this deliverable, an uncertainty factor is observable if its value can be metered and, hence, is known to the TSO for the past. This includes the infeed from power plants which are directly connected to the transmission grid ($P_{infeed,i}$) and the vertical grid load ($P_{load,i}^v$) at each grid node i . Unobservable factors cannot be metered by the TSOs directly, but a superposition of several unobservable factors can: $P_{load,i}^v$ is normally composed of unobservable factors such as renewable power infeed or load. Additionally, the problem of non-observability is critical for TSOs because certain unobservable factors influence observable factors through market activities. In order to cope with this issue, unobservable factors have to be made observable by generating additional data, so that they can be recomposed to observable factors. In the transmission grid, this concerns in particular the vertical grid load, which is at each grid node i defined as:

$$P_{load,i}^v = P_{load,i} - P_{RES,i} - P_{conv,sub,i}$$

where $P_{load,i}$ is load from households, industry etc., $P_{RES,i}$ is the underlying generation from RES and $P_{conv,sub,i}$ is the underlying generation from conventional power plants.

Furthermore, changes of factors within a control zone influence factors and their uncertainty in neighbouring control zones and beyond. This is modelled in this deliverable as the power exchange P_{exch} between control zones.

In general, the modelling of uncertainty factors can be divided into estimation and simulation. The estimation is based upon historical observations and is repeated occasionally in order to account for changing uncertainties over time. Simulation is repeated daily for operational planning.

Subsequently, the modelling of the individual uncertainty factors is described briefly. Further information can be found in [2].

3.1 Renewable power forecasts

Renewable power forecasts include underlying wind or solar power or both depending on the installed capacity in the control zone. The subsequent modelling approach requires historical RES in-feeds and forecasts at each grid node. If this kind of data is not available already, it has to be generated by the TSO. How the modelling of RES uncertainties fits into the probabilistic operational planning framework is illustrated in Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1: RES uncertainty in the probabilistic operational planning framework

As mentioned earlier, the entire process can be divided into estimation and simulation. Its structure is shown in Figure 3-2. The individual parts are elaborated subsequently.

Figure 3-2: Estimation and simulation of RES uncertainties

3.1.1 Estimation

$P_{RES,i}$ is subject to uncertainty due to imperfect deterministic forecasts $\hat{P}_{RES,i}$. Hence, a forecast error $E_{RES,i} = \hat{P}_{RES,i} - P_{RES,i}$ is made at each grid node i . In order to model the uncertainty of renewable power in-feeds, the probability distribution $F_{RES,i}(P_{RES,i})$ has to be known. At each grid node, $E_{RES,i}$ and $P_{RES,i}$ are normalized with the installed capacity at i , so that $E_{RES,i} \in [-1,1]$ and $P_{RES,i} \in [0,1]$. Thus, $\hat{P}_{RES,i} = 0$ leads to $E_{RES,i} \in [-1,0]$ and $\hat{P}_{RES,i} = 1$ to $E_{RES,i} \in [0,1]$. In order to account for this property, the conditional distribution

$F_{RES,i}(P_{RES,i}|\hat{P}_{RES,i})$ has to be estimated. Furthermore, the issue time t and the look-ahead time k (forecast time horizon) of the forecast influence the uncertainty of the deterministic forecast, so that the conditional probability density function becomes $F_{RES,i}^{t+k|t}(P_{RES,i}^{t+k|t}|\hat{P}_{RES,i}^{t+k|t})$. Given that TSOs receive their forecasts at the same time each day and that an update is not possible because measures of operational planning have to be fixed day-ahead, t can be neglected for the estimation. Finally, $F_{RES,i}^k(P_{RES,i}^k|\hat{P}_{RES,i}^k)$ should be estimated to model the uncertainty of RES forecasts adequately for operational planning. Hence, if the number of grid nodes in a control zone is I and K hours are considered for operational planning, $I \cdot K$ distributions have to be estimated. Depending on the type of relevant underlying generation from RESs, $F_{wind,i}$, $F_{solar,i}$ or both are modelled.

Practically, $F_{RES,i}^k(P_{RES,i}^k|\hat{P}_{RES,i}^k)$ is not estimated directly but $F_{RES,i}^k(E_{RES,i}^k|\hat{P}_{RES,i}^k)$ and $F_{RES,i}^{k-1}(q_{RES,i}^k|\hat{P}_{RES,i}^k)$ is added later to $\hat{P}_{RES,i}$ in the simulation process. $F_{RES,i}^k(E_{RES,i}^k|\hat{P}_{RES,i}^k)$ is estimated with a conditional kernel density estimator.

Due to the inertia of meteorological developments, which are normally a main input of RES power forecasts, forecasts are spatially correlated. This motivates the use of a copula, which describes the functional relationship between a joint distribution function and its marginals.

With $U_{RES,i}^k = F_{RES,i}^{k-1}(P_{RES,i}^k|\hat{P}_{RES,i}^k)$:

$$C_{RES,k}(U_{RES,1}^k, U_{RES,2}^k, \dots, U_{RES,I}^k) = F^k(P_{RES,1}^k, P_{RES,2}^k, \dots, P_{RES,I}^k, \rho),$$

where ρ is the copula parameter(s) of a Gaussian or t-copula. Which copula is suitable is tested with a state-of-the-art copula test [4].

Further information about the estimation of the marginal distributions and copulas can be found in [2].

3.1.2 Simulation

The simulation requires the copula $C_{RES,k}$ as input and the point prediction $\hat{P}_{RES,i}^{t+k|t}$. By drawing random numbers with $C_{RES,k}$, $P_{RES,i}^{t+k|t}$ can be simulated for each grid node i whereas the spatial correlation is accounted for by the copula. The simulation is carried out by following:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{RES,k}(U_{RES,1}^k, U_{RES,2}^k, \dots, U_{RES,I}^k) &\Rightarrow U_{RES,1}^k, U_{RES,2}^k, \dots, U_{RES,I}^k \Rightarrow F_{RES,i}^{t+k|t-1}(U_{RES,i}^k|\hat{P}_{RES,i}^{t+k|t}) \\ &\Rightarrow P_{RES,sim,i}^{t+k|t}. \end{aligned}$$

This yields the simulated underlying infeed from RES at each grid node i for the time stamp t .

3.2 Active load forecasts

Figure 3-3: Load uncertainty in the probabilistic operational planning framework

Active load plays a special role in this framework. According to the definition made in the beginning of section 3, load uncertainty absorbs the remaining uncertainty that is not caused by RES uncertainty, namely load from households, industry etc. and underlying conventional generation, and can be defined as:

$$P_{load,i} = P_{load,i}^v + P_{RES,i} + P_{conv,sub,i}.$$

If the TSO decides not to model RES individually (e.g. because of a negligible amount of RES installations), the uncertainty of $P_{load,i}$ includes the remaining RES uncertainty as well. If there is no underlying conventional generation and the RES uncertainty is modelled as in section 3.1, the uncertainty of $P_{load,i}$ contains only load from households, factories etc. The latter has been a daily forecasting routine for TSOs for decades. That is why, the uncertainty of $P_{load,i}$ is lower compared to RES uncertainty and not a major concern for operational planning. Still, an integral approach requires the modelling of load uncertainty as well.

3.2.1 Estimation

Load uncertainty data (DACFS and SNs provided by TSO partners) exhibits quite different patterns depending on the structure of the underlying load and small-scale generation. Thus, a parametric approach for modelling the uncertainty of $P_{load,i}$ is not an option. Instead, a non-parametric approach is chosen. A kernel density estimator with a Gaussian kernel performs well and is flexible enough to deal with any kind of load distribution.

Depending on the load structure, load forecast errors can be highly correlated at a given look-ahead time and, hence, the forecast uncertainty. A copula accounts for this spatial

interdependence. Therefore, $F_{P_{load,i}^k}^k(P_{load,i}^k)$ is estimated with a kernel density estimator and transformed to $U_{load,i}^k$ using the normal quantile transform, so that a copula can be fitted:

$$C_{load,k}(U_{load,1}^k, U_{load,2}^k, \dots, U_{load,I}^k) = F^k(P_{load,1}^k, P_{load,2}^k, \dots, P_{load,I}^k, \rho),$$

where ρ is the copula parameter(s) of a Gaussian or t-copula.

3.2.2 Simulation

In contrast to the simulation of RES uncertainty, load uncertainty simulation does not require point forecasts, because the distributions are not conditional on them. Instead, $C_{load,k}$ can be directly used to simulate the load uncertainty at each grid node for each look-ahead time k by following:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{load,k}(U_{load,1}^k, U_{load,2}^k, \dots, U_{load,I}^k) &\Rightarrow U_{load,1}^k, U_{load,2}^k, \dots, U_{load,I}^k \Rightarrow F_{P_{load,i}^k}^{t+k|t}{}^{-1}(U_{load,i}^{k|t}) \\ &\Rightarrow P_{load,sim,i}^{t+k|t}. \end{aligned}$$

3.3 Reactive load forecasts

The current DACF dataset includes not only forecasts of the vertical active load, but also information on reactive power in an analogous manner. However, according to information provided by TSOs this data is not used for simulations or analyses during the operational planning process. One reason to neglect the data is the limited quality. Furthermore, due to the absence of a common methodology to obtain reactive load forecasts applied by all European TSOs, the accuracy of the forecasts differs significantly. The accuracy has been evaluated by comparing historical DACF datasets with the corresponding snapshots.

In order to build a usable and complete system use case for operational planning, the DACF+ requires a forecast methodology for reactive power $Q_{load,i}^{t+k|t}$ at each node i , which is:

- valid for all European TSOs,
- provides an adequate accuracy,
- capable of considering changes in the system.

This also enables TSOs to perform static voltage stability analyses.

To add to the complexity of the reactive load forecast $Q_{load,i}^k$, its uncertainty $F_{Q_{load,i}^k}^k(Q_{load,i}^k)$ is higher compared to the active power forecast due to several direct interdependences, such as:

- existing system components such as overhead-lines and cables,
- the topology of the transmission system, and
- the active and reactive loads in subordinate grids.

In the past, the forecast of the reactive power was comparably simple and straight-forward. Due to the lower amount of distributed generation, TSOs were able to forecast the active load based on standardized load profiles. Based on those profiles, the reactive load was

calculated assuming either a constant power factor or, if a more accurate forecast was required, standardized power factor profiles or aggregated reactive power profiles as described in [5]. These methods are not accurate enough in a power system with a high penetration of RES, due to the influence of the RES caused by.

- the active power infeed from RES units connected to sub-transmission voltage levels, that influenced load flows in subordinate grids and, hence, the reactive power, and
- the reactive power injected from RES, especially wind farms.

These are effects which cannot be modelled by the previously described methods to forecast reactive loads and motivate the development of a new forecasting tool. Given the dependencies that influence $Q_{load,i}^k$ and $F_{Q_{load,i}}^k(Q_{load,i}^k)$ and the low quality of the reactive load forecast, it is necessary to generate a deterministic and probabilistic reactive load forecast.

3.3.1 Estimation

As mentioned earlier, $Q_{load,i}^{t+k|t}$ depends directly on other influencing factors, which are already modelled within this framework, namely:

- Forecasted wind power infeed at node i ,
- Forecasted solar power infeed at node i , and
- Forecasted active power at node i .

Besides, the day-ahead value $Q_{load,i}^{t-24+k|t-24}$ is used to account for autocorrelation and the hour of the day and type of the day is incorporated to capture seasonal and diurnal patterns. Hence, the point forecast $Q_{load,i}^{t+k|t}$ can be expressed as function of its influencing parameters:

$$Q_{load,i}^{t+k|t} = f\left(Q_{load,i}^{t-24+k|t-24}, \hat{P}_{load,i}^{t+k|t}, \hat{P}_{RES,i}^{t+k|t}, hod, tod\right),$$

where hod represents the hour of the day and tod the type of the day (weekday, weekend or holiday).

Due to the mentioned complexities and non-linear relationships between the influencing factors, traditional time series methods cannot be applied. Instead, artificial neuronal networks (ANNs) are used to predict $Q_{load,i}^{t+k|t}$. Figure 3-4 shows the structure of the ANN. Cross validation is applied during training to avoid over-fitting of the ANN. 80% of the data

is used to train the ANN and 20% is used for the validation, whereas the data is split randomly.

Figure 3-4: Scheme of ANN

Besides the nodes with a high underlying share of renewable energies, other particular nodes, such as pump storage nodes, have a non-standard PQ profile. However, this can be handled properly by ANNs as well. Appendix A shows and analyzes some typical PQ profiles.

3.3.2 Simulation

The estimated relationships can be used to determine directly the reactive load:

$$Q_{load, sim.i}^{t+k|t} = f \left(Q_{load,i}^{t-24+k|t-24}, P_{load, sim.i}^{t+k|t}, P_{RES, sim.i}^{t+k|t}, hod, tod \right),$$

whereas simulation results for $P_{load, sim.i}^{t+k|t}$ and $P_{RES, sim.i}^{t+k|t}$ are used. Hence, the deterministic estimator can be applied to model the uncertainty of reactive load by taking uncertainty simulations as an input. How this is incorporated into the DACF+ process is elaborated in appendix A. In addition, appendix a contains exemplary results of the reactive load forecast model.

3.4 Power exchange with neighbouring systems/control areas

Figure 5: Power exchange uncertainty in the probabilistic operational planning framework

A forecast of future system states requires predictions on those parameters which influence the system state. The approach for power generation by RES and loads are described in the previous sections of this document. However, the exchange with neighboring parts of the European Transmission System has an influence on the system state. Thus, it has to be considered as well and is addressed subsequently. How this is incorporated into the probabilistic operational planning framework is depicted in Figure 5.

The “European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity” (entso-e) publishes a day-ahead forecast for the power exchange between those control areas being members of entso-e. The sum of all exchanges with neighbors produces the balance of the respective control area. However, since this forecast is generated one day in advance it does not include e.g. the results of intraday trading activities. Given the fact that the volume of electrical energy traded in this market is significant, the deviation between the day-ahead forecast and the actual values is important for a realistic assessment of future system states. Furthermore, it can be assumed that the exchange of electrical power between control areas will further increase in the future due to the effort made by the European Union to implement one common European market for electrical energy.

The forecast of the control area balance acts as an input parameter for the intraday-day module which is part of the approach presented in this document. Therefore, the error of the day-ahead exchange forecast (DAEF) compared to the actual power flow (APF) has to be modelled. The approach for the European control areas balancing model (ECAB) is presented and discussed in the following sections.

Starting with the background for the modelling of the power exchange between European control areas, the objective of the model is described in the next section of this chapter. After that, the specification of the model and the approach which is chosen to predict the forecast

error and the control area balances, respectively, is presented and discussed. The proof of concept is carried out based on exemplary results for different years in the past and various control areas.

3.4.1 Estimation

3.4.1.1 Background

The DAEF as well as the APF is available on the entso-e transparency platform [source: <https://transparency.entsoe.eu>]. The deviation between these two parameters is depicted for a timespan of three days and the control area Slovenia in Figure 3-6.

Figure 3-6: Deviation between DAEF and APF (Slovenia)

The balance of the control area Slovenia is shown on the y-axis whereas the timespan considered can be found on the x-axis. A negative balance of the control area means that electrical energy is imported whilst a positive balance is the result of an export of electrical energy from this control area.

The balance forecasted the day before for Slovenia leads to an import of electrical energy for almost the entire timespan analysed here in this example. However, the sum of the APFs leads to a significant number of hours with a net export of electrical energy. Furthermore, the sum of the APFs does not exceed +/- 500 MW, but the forecast predicted a maximum difference of more than -1000 MW.

3.4.1.2 Objective

The objective here is the development of a model which is capable of predicting the error of the day-ahead forecast of power exchanges between control areas and the resulting balances of these control areas. In order to achieve this objective, constraints have to be considered.

The first constraint is the availability and quality of data available. The data provided by the entso-e transparency platform (see previous section) does include a limited number of control areas in Europe only.

The second constraint is the fact that the sum of the balances of all control areas has to be zero. Based on the data provided by entso-e the second constraint is only valid for a selection of European control areas. Therefore, the ECAB can be used for the following selection of control areas/countries:

- Great Britain
- Spain
- France
- Belgium
- The Netherlands
- Sweden 3 + 4
- Norway 1 + 2
- Denmark 1 + 2
- Germany (considered as one control area)
- Switzerland
- Austria
- Italy
- Poland
- Czech Republic
- Slovakia
- Slovenia
- Hungary

The selection is depicted in Figure 3-7.

Figure 3-7: Selected countries/control areas for ECAB model

The sum of all balances within the colored area is zero for every hour. This is not valid for the inclusion of additional countries.

3.4.1.3 *Specification of the model*

In addition to the objective and the constraints to be considered additional factors influence the development of the model. First of all, it is aspired to use a limited set of input data to run the model and to achieve the desired results. Furthermore, the input dataset should be publicly available. Secondly, the usability of the model has a high priority since the model serves “only” as a tool to gather the necessary information for the prediction and identification of critical system states. Therefore, the computation must stay within a timespan which allows an application in the operational planning process executed by TSOs. Lastly, a modular approach is preferred in order to ensure the expandability of the model. For instance, if additional information will be available in the near future it should be possible to include this information to improve the quality of the model output.

3.4.1.4 Approach and methodology

The objective and the corresponding framework for the model suggest an approach based on statistical methods. However, due to the fact that the objective of the reactive load model which has been described before (see section 3.3), is a similar one, the application of an artificial neural network (ANN) has been tested for this purpose as well.

The ANN is trained with data from the previous year and is capable of predicting the DAEF error for the next day. In order to meet the requirements for system state forecasting, a deterministic as well as a probabilistic set of input parameters can be used.

The process for the deterministic use case is shown in Figure 3-8.

Figure 3-8: Flow chart of the ECAB with deterministic input data

The process consists of two parts. The part on the left hand side of Figure 3-8 has to be executed at least a couple of hours in advance. The training of the ANN is the core function of this offline part. The user has to define the year for which the ANN has to be trained. In general, the year to be chosen here is the year before the current one. This information is used to select the relevant data for the training of the ANN from the database. A total number of A ANNs is trained. In the current version of the model, A equals 20 based on the selection of countries presented in section 3.4.1.2.

The trained ANNs serve as an input factor for the online part of the ECAB depicted on the right hand side of Figure 3-8. The online process of the ECAB starts with a user input. The

required information includes the definition of the time period for which the model should predict the forecast error. The time period is defined by the start and stop time (year, month, day and hour) and comprises x hours.

Furthermore, the control areas/countries to be considered by the model have to be specified by the user.

The next two steps of the online process will be according to the user defined time period executed x times. The first step is the allocation of forecast data of the infeed by RES and the load for the respective hour from the database. The forecast data serves as an input for the A trained ANNs. The results are $A \cdot x$ predictions of the day-ahead forecast error for the A control areas/countries selected by the user.

For process for the probabilistic use case is very similar to the deterministic one described in Figure 3-8. Figure 3-9 below provides an overview of the probabilistic process.

Figure 3-9: Flow chart of the ECAB with probabilistic input data

The offline process is the same for both use cases. The only difference between the two processes lies in the online part. In contrast to the deterministic process, the input data for the trained ANNs consists of n samples of forecasts for the infeed by RES and the load. Hence, the number of predictions for the day-ahead forecast error is $A \cdot n \cdot x$.

3.4.1.5 Training of artificial neural networks

Before the model can be used for the prediction of the forecast error, the artificial neural networks for each of the 20 control areas/countries has to be trained with historical data. In general, the concept is the same as for the model predicting the reactive load (see section 3.4.1.2). For the application here, two different setups are implemented and tested. The first approach uses a minimum of input data whilst the second one aims to increase the forecast accuracy by using an extended set of input data. The scheme of the training for the reduced data requirements is depicted in Figure 3-10 below.

Figure 3-10: Scheme of ANN training (limited input data set)

The input vector for the ANN training contains the information on the respective hour, the day of the week and the day ahead forecast. The actual physical flow acts as a reference.

The extended model using additional input data is shown in Figure 2-5. Exemplary results are presented in appendix B.

Figure 3-11: Scheme of ANN training (extended input data set)

In addition to the input data used for the approach illustrated in Figure 2-4 above, the approach using an extended input data set includes the day ahead forecast for wind and pv-in-feeds as well as for the load in Germany. Of course, it would be possible to include specific data for each country/control area considered. However, the results presented in the next section are already promising. Therefore, an inclusion of country-specific is part of further research.

3.4.2 Simulation

Similar to the uncertainty modelling of reactive load, the uncertainty of the power exchange can be modelled directly by running the ANN with input that is already available:

$$\Delta P_{EXC,sim,z}^{t+k|t} = f \left(\sum_i \hat{P}_{load,i}^{v,t+k|t}, \sum_i \hat{P}_{wind,i}^{t+k|t}, \sum_i \hat{P}_{solar,i}^{t+k|t}, \hat{P}_{EXC,z}^{t+k|t}, hod, dow \right).$$

By running the model N -times a distribution of possible power exchanges can be derived.

3.5 Short-term trading

Unforeseen changes on the load side and of imports and exports lead inevitably to trades in the intraday markets. Thus, where, when and to which extend these trades take place is uncertain as well and affects $P_{infeed,i}$. The integration of these uncertainties into the probabilistic operational planning framework can be seen in Figure 3-12. Because the condition $\sum_i P_{infeed,i} = \sum_i P_{load,i}^v$ must hold in the transmission grid as well and the uncertainty of P_{load}^v is modelled, we can focus merely on the modeling of the intraday players that are connected to the transmission grid. The quantity of intraday trades and their occurrence at $t + k$ is given by:

$$\Delta P_{infeed}^{t+k|t} = \Delta P_{load}^{v,t+k|t} = \Delta P_{EXC,sim,z}^{t+k|t} + \sum_i \hat{P}_{load,i}^{v,t+k|t} - P_{load,sim,i}^{v,t+k|t}$$

At which node i a change of power output occurs is computed by a merit order model. Therefore, the merit order of all power plants connected to the transmission grid has to be replicated. The power plants schedules that are handed over to the TSOs by power plant operators one day-ahead are the main input.

Figure 3-12: Short-term trading uncertainty in the probabilistic operational planning framework

In order to account for power plant outages, the probability of becoming unavailable (time to fail (TTF)) is modelled with an exponential distribution:

$$f_{TTF}(TTF, \mu) = \frac{1}{\mu} * e^{-\frac{TTF}{\mu}}$$

If $t \geq 0$. The distribution parameter μ is the mean time to fail (MTTF) in hours. By drawing random numbers for $F_{TTF}(TTF, \mu)$ and getting the inverse distribution function, $TTF = F_{TTF}^{-1}(q, \mu)$ can be computed. If $TTF \leq k$, the unit becomes unavailable at $t + k$ and is not considered in the merit order model.

Figure 3-13: Merit order model

With additional power plant specific parameters, e.g. efficiency and fuel type, the merit order can be replicated as shown in Figure 3-13. An evaluation of test runs has shown that the estimate of certain power plant specific parameters has a huge influence on the quality of results. E.g., if the marginal costs are not estimated well, a power plant in a completely different part of the control zone might adjust its power production instead the one that actual adjusted its power production in reality. In order to account for this additional endogenous uncertainty, a stochastic merit order is implemented. Thereby, the marginal costs are varied uniformly distributed between 95 and 105 % of the marginal cost estimate.

Finally, $\Delta P_{load}^{v,t+k|t}$ can be used to compute $\Delta P_{infeed,i}^{t+k|t}$ based upon the merit order, what yields the change in power production at each node i for each time stamp $t + k$. Naturally, this process has to be repeated for or each simulation sim . The process to determine

$\Delta P_{infeed,i}^{t+k|t}$ is depicted in Figure 3-14.

Figure 3-14: Computation of power plant production changes

4 Merging of uncertainties and computation of system state parameter distributions

Once all uncertainty factors are described, they have to be merged in a way that a load flow calculation can be run, what yields system state parameters. The procedure of merging uncertainties and the necessary steps are described in section 4.1. Section 4.2 discusses the handling of remaining uncertainties, which have not been modelled in chapter 3. Finally, section 4.3 focuses on the computation of system state parameter distributions.

4.1 Simulation of uncertainties in operational planning

In this section, the re-composition of uncertainty factors is implemented in a way that they can be further processed. The main application will be a load flow calculation, what requires vertical loads and in-feeds at each grid node and for each timestamp.

Active vertical grid load at each node i is modelled by a combination of underlying RES generation (cf. section 3.1) and the remaining vertical grid load (cf. section 3.2):

$$P_{load,sim,i}^{v,t+k|t} = P_{load,sim,i}^{t+k|t} - P_{RES,sim,i}^{t+k|t}$$

$Q_{load,sim,i}^{v,t+k|t}$ is computed according to the model presented in section 3.3. Subsequently, $\Delta P_{load,sim,z}^{v,t+k|t}$ for one control zone z and other parameters are used to model the deviation of the control zone balance using the ECAB model (cf. section 3.4). This yields the remainder of uncertainty that has to be balanced by the intraday market:

$$\Delta P_{load,sim,z}^{t+k|t} = \Delta P_{EXC,sim,z}^{t+k|t} + \sum_i \Delta P_{load,i}^{v,t+k|t}$$

Then, the merit order model (cf. section 0) is applied to determine $P_{infeed,sim,i}^{t+k|t}$. In summary, the following steps have to be carried out:

1. simulate RES and load uncertainty,
2. run the ECAB model and
3. run the merit order model.

By repeating this for each look-ahead hour k and N simulations, a Monte Carlo simulation can be performed and used as an input for multiple applications. This is exemplarily shown for the intraday trading part in Figure 4-1, where $P_{load,sim,i}^{v,t+k|t}$ is available as input.

Figure 4-1: Intraday trading program

4.2 System balance and operating reserves

After all relevant uncertainty factors are modelled, merged and simulated, the condition $\Delta P_{load,sim,z}^{t+k|t} = \Delta P_{infeed,sim,z}^{t+k|t}$ must hold for each control zone z . Hence, the remaining uncertainty in the system and, therefore, the system balance is theoretically zero. However, a few other uncertainties, which have been neglected due to their minor impact, are still present. Besides failures of system components, system losses will be different compared to the deterministic DACF. In this framework, it is assumed that the remaining uncertainties are handled by the operating reserves.

4.3 Load flow calculation and computation of system state parameter distributions

Given the uncertainties, the computation of system state parameters and their distributions requires to run load flow calculations. Depending on the maximum number of Monte Carlo simulations N , the same number of load flow calculations has to be performed. The entire process is displayed in Figure 4-2. First, the uncertainty factors have to be simulated as stated in chapter 3, which is represented by the gray box. This yields the values of the vertical grid load $P_{load,sim,i}^{v,t+k|t}$ and infeed $P_{infeed,sim,i}^{t+k|t}$ at each grid node. Subsequently, a load flow calculation is run and the system state parameters are computed. Thereby, the system state parameter *voltage* exists at each node, meanwhile *branch current* is computed for each line. After repeating this process N -times, distributions representing all possible system states at time stamp $t + k$ (t : time of forecast issue, k : look-ahead time) are computed.

Figure 4-2: Computation of system state parameter distributions

5 Forecasting of critical system states

Computing distributions of system state parameters is time-consuming, meanwhile time is a scarce resource in operational planning. Besides that, some computed system states are not critical and, hence, provide no additional information to the TSOs. By identifying the critical system states only and linking the forecast condition to the occurrence of critical system states, they can be forecasted. Therefore, section 5.1 elaborates how critical system states are defined. Methods for forecasting critical systems states are presented in section 5.2.

5.1 Definition of critical system states

In general, a system state can be considered to be critical if an operational limit is exceeded. Within the nowadays regulatory framework, the N-1 criterion is the sole rule for assessing the reliability of a power grid. Hence, a contingency analysis applying the N-1 criterion is used to identify critical system states. Thereby, each simulation *sim* requires its own contingency analysis. Each simulation run which leads to a violation of the N-1 criterion is considered to be critical. This procedure of identifying critical system states is exemplarily shown for the system parameter node voltage in Figure 5-1. The red dotted line represents the distribution of simulated voltages at a certain node. All dots (system states) which are inside the green interval are non-critical and, hence, are not further analyzed.

Figure 5-1: Exemplary identification of critical system states

Furthermore, other reliability criterion, e.g. risk-based approaches, can be implemented easily. In this framework, the measure of criticality is designed as a module which can be exchanged. The resulting dataset consisting of N Monte Carlo simulations has to cover all

potentially critical system states. Furthermore, a significant number of non-critical system states are included in the Monte Carlo simulations. This aspect is discussed in the following section.

5.2 Forecasting and identification of critical system states

This section is concerned with the identification of a set of critical system states $S_{critical}$, which is a subset of all possible system states $S_{critical} \subset S$. In order to differentiate between the hours of the forecast horizon in operational planning, different critical system state sets have to be introduced for each look-ahead time k . Because decisions have to be made in t , this becomes a forecasting problem that aims at predicting $S_{critical}^{t+k|t} \subset S^{t+k|t}$ for each k . Subsequently, three approaches for forecasting $S_{critical}^{t+k|t}$ are presented.

5.2.1 Full computation

The full computation approach aims at computing all system states $S^{t+k|t} \forall k$ and identifying securely the critical ones by running a N-1 contingency analysis. Efficient algorithms for solving the load flow problem have to be applied due to the size of the problem. Furthermore, a high level of parallelization is necessary to forecast all critical systems states in a satisfying amount of time. However, the full computation approach represents the only approach that is capable of forecasting all critical system states correctly under the assumption that the simulated distribution of system state parameters covers all likely system state parameters in reality.

5.2.2 Problems of dimensionality and computation time

In order to perform a contingency analysis, as many load-flow calculations as number of contingencies n_c have to be performed. This is naturally necessary for all simulations N . Hence, this corresponds to $n_c \cdot N$ load flow calculations. Because operational planning is carried out for the next K hours, $n_c \cdot N \cdot K$ load flow calculations are necessary for the whole operational planning process. If the number of contingencies is 500, 1000 Monte Carlos simulations are run and a load flow calculation takes about 1 second, the computation of all system states takes approximately 140 days without any parallel computing. Thus, the computation of all system states is under normal circumstances too time-consuming for operational planning unless the process is parallelized. The following sections present potential approaches to solve this issue and reduce the computational time accordingly.

5.2.3 Identification of non-critical system states

As can be seen in historical data sets, certain forecast conditions, such as high or low expected wind in-feeds, lead to certain distributions of system states and, hence, to certain

critical system states. Thus, the relationship between critical system states $S_{critical}^{t+k|t}$ and the respective set of forecast conditions $C^{t+k|t} \subset C$ can be replicated by a function:

$$S_{critical}^{t+k|t} = f(C^{t+k|t}, S_{critical}^{historical}, C^{historical}),$$

which uses historical critical system states $S_{critical}^{historical}$ and forecast conditions $C^{historical}$ in order to learn the functional relationship. The relationship can be used to identify the set of uncritical system states $S_{uncritical} \subset S$, which consists of system states that do not exceed any operational limit.

Figure 5-2: Set of all system states S and the subsets $S_{non-critical}$, $S_{reduced}$ and $S_{critical}$

The idea is to reduce the number of the system states that have to be evaluated in term of criticality, which is illustrated in Figure 5-2. Thereby, a reduced subset $S_{reduced} \subset (S \setminus S_{uncritical})$ is formed. $S_{reduced}$ can be understood as a buffer zone in order to make sure that none of the critical system states are missed. Besides, $S_{reduced}$ helps to understand how the system reacts when it is approaching a critical system state. The reduced subset can be either fully computed (cf. section 5.2.1) or serve as the input for a selective approach, which is outlined in section 5.2.4.

The most promising approach is the application of a pattern recognition methodology. However, a broad data base is required to minimize the probability to assign a critical system state to the group of uncritical ones by mistake. Furthermore, it has to be ensured that those system states which have never occurred in the past are assigned to the correct set of system states.

5.2.4 Selective approach

Reducing the number of system states to be evaluated is the first step to reduce the computation time. However, this first step does not provide the critical system states relevant for the operational planning process. The problem with any approach other than the analytical one described as “full computation” in section 5.2.1 is to ensure that all critical system states are identified securely, i.e. not to assign a critical system state to the group of the uncritical ones. However, in practice it will not be possible to limit the reduced set of

system states $S_{reduced}$ to the number of the critical ones but to further reduce this set to a number of “suspicious” system states by using additional information and to use mathematical operations, which are efficient in terms of the required computational time. The concept is outlined in Figure 5-3.

Figure 5-3: Forecasting critical system states

6 Conclusions

Modeling of uncertainties for power systems requires the consideration of many factors. There are furthermore many interdependences between these factors (e.g. between RES infeed and power exchange), which make the modeling a truly complex undertaking. At the same time, the information derived using the complex models has to be reduced to a level that is useful to the people doing the actual power system operation.

The approach developed here allows to cope in detail and without restrictive assumptions for the various uncertain factors and their combined distribution characteristics have been approximated as good as possible. This input is used then to determine load flows and system states in a next step. This requires a dedicated thinking about what are the relevant system states and an adequate handling of the numerous input data. Finally this is then used for the identification of critical system states. Here it is clearly shown that no unique approach is to be recommended but several pathways have been developed with each having its specific drawbacks and merits. They clearly complement each other and depending on the system under study and the conditions of operation one or another may be chosen.

By providing hence a general approach based on parameter estimations, Monte Carlo simulations and identification techniques, work package 2 provides core input for future secure operation of power systems with high penetration of renewables. At the same time the framework developed may easily be adapted to changing circumstances or better data quality and availability in the future.

Appendix A

PQ-analysis for forecasting reactive vertical load

An analysis of the PQ characteristics is necessary in order to evaluate the performance of the reactive load forecasting model. Therefore, the PQ characteristics depend heavily on the situation in the subordinate voltage levels. This is illustrated in Figure A-1, whereas P_{RAL} (RAL) represents the residual (or underlying) active load and Q_{RRL} (RRL) the residual (or underlying) reactive load.

Figure A-1: Simplified representation of underlying voltage levels

Figure A-2 **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** shows a PQ-diagram, a scatterplot of the values of RAL (x-axis) and RRL (y-axis) measured in one year in 15 minute time-steps at one node of the transmission system.

Figure A-2: PQ-Diagram of a transmission system node with a small amount of installed RES (node 1)

The sign convention applied for the division of the quadrants of Figure A-2 is depicted in Figure A-3.

Figure A-3: Sign convention for quadrants

Positive (negative) values of the RRL in quadrants I and II (II and IV) represent inductive (capacitive) loads from the perspective of the transmission system. The RAL only shows positive values, which means that the subordinate voltage levels consists of active power consumers (quadrants I and IV) with a negligible amount of installed RES units.

The analysis of the RRL time series shows similarities to the analysis of the RAL, such as pronounced daily cycles with significant differences between working days, Saturdays and Sundays/public holidays, characteristics which arise from the cyclical patterns of human behavior. Figure A-4 shows such patterns for a time period of one week, starting with Saturday. The third day has a similar pattern to day one and two because this Monday was a local holiday.

Figure A-4: Exemplary Time Series of RAL (blue) and RRL (red)

An exemplary node 2, shown in Figure A-5, is located in the north of Germany in a region where a substantial amount of wind energy units are connected to the distribution system. The negative values of the RAL correspond to situations in which the load flow at the interconnection between transmission system and the distribution system changes direction, i.e. a surplus of active power from the subordinate voltage level is injected into the transmission system. Methods such as time series analysis cannot be applied for transmission nodes with a significant installed capacity of RES in the subordinate voltage levels as shown in Figure A-5, since the infeed from wind and solar energy units depends on the weather situation and does not follow a daily cycle. For such nodes a model has to consider the forecasted infeed from wind and solar energy units in order to predict the RRL.

Figure A-5: PQ-Diagram of a transmission system node with a significant amount of installed DG (node 2)

Figure A- 6 shows PQ scatterplots for different nodes of the German transmission system and illustrates the heterogeneity of the relation between RRL and RAL for the different nodes. This motivates the implementation of a nodal approach with one optimized model to forecast the RRL for each node.

Figure A- 6: PQ Scatterplots of different transmission system nodes

The analysis of the input data motivates the usage of models based on artificial intelligence such as artificial neural networks (ANN). ANNs are able to model multivariate relations – linear and non-linear – between several input and output variables through training.

Structure of the reactive load forecast model

The general structure of the forecast model is shown in Figure A-7. The model consists of an offline and an online part. The offline part, which is shown on the left hand side of Figure A-7, comprises the training of the ANN with historical information taken from a database. For each node of the relevant transmission system, an ANN is trained. Various tests led to the result that the training should be done with historical data from the previous year only, i.e. a forecast for a specified time horizon in year Y requires a database for training purposes from year Y-1. The inclusion of additional years (e.g. Y-2, Y-3 etc.) increases the effort regarding the database but does not lead to a significant increase of the forecast accuracy.

The online part of the model on the right hand side of Figure A-7 starts with an input by the user of the model. The user has to define the time span for which a forecast is desired. The model has to be executed x-times according to the number of hours x defined by the user. The online part requires, besides the trained ANNs for all relevant nodes of the system, measurements of present system parameters as well as the day-ahead forecast values of expected system parameters.

The present system parameters as well as the forecasted values are used as input variables to forecast the RRL during the online process.

Figure A-7: Flow chart of the reactive load forecast model (Q-Model) with deterministic input data

Figure A-7 shows the application of the model with deterministic input data as it is used for the current DACF process. Thus, the reactive load forecast model can already be used by TSOs for the existing processes.

In addition and in line with the methodology presented in section 3.3, the model can be used with probabilistic input data as well. The corresponding process is depicted in Figure A-8.

Figure A-8: Flow chart of the reactive load forecast model (Q-Model) with deterministic input data

The only difference between the two applications is the different numbers of input parameters used. Here, a total number of n forecast samples are used instead of one deterministic forecast. Accordingly, the output consists of $K * n * x$ forecasts.

Exemplary results of the reactive load forecast model

To evaluate the accuracy of the forecast, the day-ahead forecast of the RRL is calculated for a period of one week and compared to the RRL measurement. Figure A-9 and Figure A-10 show the time series of the RRL measured (blue), the output of the ANN (red) and the time series from the DACF process (green) for two nodes with different characteristics. The data used for this evaluation was not part of the training.

Figure A-9: Time series of measurement and day-ahead forecast of RRL - node 1

Figure A-10: Time series of measurement and day-ahead forecast of RRL - node 2

The error measures show higher deviations compared to the values during training. The main reason for this deviation is the forecast error of the input data RAL, wind and solar power in-feeds, which is propagated to the ANN and increases the forecast error of the RRL. This effect is more pronounced for node 2 with a high amount of installed wind-energy units, because a forecast error for the wind-energy-infeed has a higher impact on the calculated

RRL for this node. The coefficient of determination is 0.81 for node 1 and 0.18 for node 2, which reflects the aforementioned reasons.

Moreover, the PQ-diagram in Figure A-11 can also be used to evaluate the goodness of the ANN model visually. The blue dots in the PQ-diagram represent the historical data of RAL and RRL used for training and the red dots represent the output values of the ANN. Figure A-11 also shows that the general relationship between input and output data can be modeled with high accuracy using the ANN.

Figure A-11: PQ-Scatterplot: measurement and ANN output – node 2

Appendix B

Exemplary results of the ECAB

Figure B-1 shows the output of the trained ANN for Slovenia. The training has been carried out with the limited input data set.

Figure B-1: Deviation between ANN output and APF (Slovenia)

The control area balance in MW is shown on the y-axis, whereas the forecast horizon can be obtained from the x-axis. Figure 3-6. The APF is depicted in blue and the output of the ANN in red. The forecast errors of the DAEF and ANN output are compared in Figure B-2.

Figure B-2: Forecast Errors of DAEF and ANN

The errors of the two forecasts are shown on the y-axis whilst the x-axis still covers the forecast horizon. The dotted line represents the APF and thus, a perfect forecast. It is obvious that the forecast error of the ANN is significantly smaller than the deviation between the DAEF and the APF. The average hourly forecast error is some 469 MW for the DAEF and some 120 MW for ANN.

The exemplary results show that the model based on ANN is capable to predict the APF with an improved accuracy compared to the DAEF. Furthermore, the forecast error of the DAEF can be approximated.

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